

INTERNATIONALISMS OF ENGLISH ORIGIN AND THEIR ASSIMILATION IN UZBEK

Abdulla Eshkuvatovich Khudaykulov

Docent of the Termez State University

e-mail: axudayqulov@tersu.uz

ABSTRACT:

Today in the globalization world all languages interrelate with others, in the result of which they borrow elements of other languages. Borrowing is as one of the most productive ways of enriching vocabulary. They come in the result of language contact, which is the social and linguistic phenomenon by which users of different languages interact with one another, leading to a transfer of linguistic features.

In the results of language contacts of English and Uzbek languages many English words, phrases, even suffixes were borrowed and is being borrowed. Most of them are international words. In other words they denote same meaning in several languages. The given work is dedicated to study the of international words of English origin, their etymology and assimilation, their role in the development of English-Uzbek language contacts.

Keywords: language contacts, borrowings, international words, assimilation.

ANNOTATSIYA:

Bugungi globallashuv dunyosida tillararo aloqalar natijasida boshqa tillarning elementlarini o'zlashtirishi tabiiy jarayon sifatida qaraladi. So'z o'zlashtirish til lug'atini boyitishning eng samarali usullaridan biri sanaladi. Ular til bilan aloqa qilish natijasida yuzaga keladi, bu ijtimoiy va lingvistik hodisa bo'lib, turli tillardan foydalanuvchilarning bir-biri bilan o'zaro ta'siri, lingvistik xususiyatlarning ko'chishiga olib keladi.

Ingliz va o'zbek tillarining tillararo aloqalari natijalarida ko'plab inglizcha so'zlar, iboralar, hatto qo'shimchalar o'zlashtirilgan va o'zlashtirilmoqda. Ularning aksariyati baynalminal so'zlardir. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, ular bir nechta tillarda bir xil ma'noni bildiradi. Ushbu ish kelib chiqishiga ko'ra ingliz tiliga mansub bo'lgan baynalminal so'zlarni, ularning etimologiyasi va assimilyatsiyasini, ingliz-o'zbek tillari aloqalarini rivojlantirishdagi rolini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: til aloqalari, o'zlashmalar, baynalminalo so'zlar, assimilyatsiya.

Penetration of borrowed elements to the vocabulary of a certain language depends upon the history of recipient language, being conditioned by direct linguistic contacts and political, economic, diplomatic and cultural ties between nations. In linguistics and scientific literature the terms “borrowed words” and “loan-words” are used as synonyms.

Today in the globalization world all languages interrelate with others, in the result of which they can influence to the pronunciation, vocabulary, writing and other aspects of the contacting languages. Uzbek language also was under the influence of Arabic, Persian, Russian and other languages during its historical development. Thousands of words were borrowed from those languages, and borrowing became as one of the most productive ways of enriching vocabulary.

The latest researches deeper study borrowings and divide them into following groups: exotic words, barbarisms, internationalisms, foreign inclusions, calques.

Among other types of borrowings of English origin internationalisms or international words play an important role in the development of English-Uzbek language contacts.

Language contact is the social and linguistic phenomenon by which users of different languages (or different dialects of the same language) interact with one another, leading to a transfer of linguistic features. Contact may occur between languages, which are genetically related or unrelated, speakers may have similar or vastly different social structures, and patterns of multilingualism may also vary greatly.

The development of the contacts between nations and the dominance of English language in the globalization era caused to borrowing of some lexical units into Uzbek. The penetration history of English borrowings into Uzbek dates back to the end of XIX century and the beginning of the XX century.

The English borrowings partially touched in the works of following Uzbek scholars: M.Mirzaev [7], R.Doniyorov [2], E.M.Davlyatova [1,11] and others. Most of them included English borrowings in the group of Russian-international words and their researches prove that the English words came into Uzbek through Russian.

In linguistics, an internationalism or international word is a loanword that occurs in several languages (that is, translingually) with the same or at least similar meaning and etymology.

At the end of XX century, especially, after the proclamation of Independence in Uzbekistan, many international words of English origin directly entered into

Uzbek vocabulary in the result of language contacts. For example, дилер [Engl. dealer], бизнес маркази [Engl. Business center], брокер [Engl. broker]; бартер [Engl. barter], демпинг [Engl. dumping], дефолт [Engl. default], лизинг [Engl. leasing], холдинг [Engl. holding], форвардер [Engl. forwarder] and many others.

In the first decade of the XXIst century many anglicisms have appeared in the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. Analysis of official business documents shows that the number of Anglicisms related to the spheres of economics, science and technology is greater than in other areas. Many economic terms of English origin хеджирлаш [Engl. Hedging], ассисмент [Engl. assessment], онлайн [Engl. online], офлайн [Engl. offline], вайфай [Engl. Wi-fi] and many others penetrated into the Uzbek language in the beginning of the XXIst century [4,5,8,9].

«Масофадан ўқитиш усуллари асосидаги такрорий курсларда тингловчиларнинг ассисмент топшириқлари (жорий назорат) онлайн шаклида ташкиллаштирилади» [14].

Most of them are international words or “internationalisms”. Internationalisms are lexemes that function in many languages and are similar in external form (taking into account phonetic and graphic correspondences) and meaning. For example: Uzb. ассисмент/ Engl. Assessment.

“International words” are words that have been borrowed from one language and are used across multiple languages with similar meanings. These words often originate from dominant or widely influential languages, such as English, and spread due to globalization, technology, science, trade, and cultural influence.

The layer of international vocabulary of English origin is one of the most voluminous. The English language influences the development of world culture, since the processes occurring in the language cannot be separated from the main trends in the life of the nation. The globalization of the English language contributes to the spread of moral values of English speaking countries [8,9,10,12].

The study of international words existing in the vocabulary of Russian and Uzbek languages, actually important to understand their modern conditions. Together with the synchronic studies of borrowings, diachronic studies dedicated to their etymology and dynamic are also important, in order to possess full imagination about borrowings.

According to the etymological principle (the possibility or impossibility of accurately establishing the time and source of borrowing, on the one hand, and the area of the word in the vocabulary of modern languages, on the other hand), all

borrowed words belong to two groups: actually foreign borrowings and international vocabulary” [5].

Borrowings of English origin came to Uzbek in the result of English-Uzbek language contacts. The term “language contact” was forwarded first by U.Weinreich [13] and other scientists have developed it. The studies carried out on language contacts permit to set the traces of a certain word. According to studies every loan word assimilates to the inner regulations of the recipient language.

The assimilation of English borrowings in the Uzbek language involves several linguistic processes that allow foreign words to fit more naturally into Uzbek’s phonetic, grammatical, and orthographic systems. In many cases, borrowed English words are adapted to align with Uzbek phonological rules. For example, complex consonant clusters or sounds that are not native to Uzbek may be simplified or modified — such as the word manager becoming menedjer, where the pronunciation is adjusted to match Uzbek phonotactics.

Additionally, morphological assimilation is observed when English nouns take on Uzbek grammatical endings. Borrowed terms are often inflected with Uzbek suffixes to indicate case, number, or possession (e.g., marketga – «to the market», with the Uzbek dative case suffix -ga).

Orthographically, many English borrowings are transliterated using the Latin-based Uzbek alphabet, sometimes preserving the original spelling partially or fully, depending on the context. For instance, terms like kompyuter, internet, and brend appear in Uzbek texts with slight modifications to reflect local spelling conventions. Over time, some borrowed words become fully integrated and no longer feel foreign to native speakers, especially when they are widely used across media, education, and daily life.

Assimilation can also vary depending on the speaker’s level of exposure to English or the domain in which the borrowing is used. Technical and academic fields often retain English terms with minimal changes, while in informal contexts, more localized adaptations are common. This ongoing process reflects the dynamic nature of language and the balancing act between maintaining linguistic identity and embracing global communication trends.

The assimilation of English borrowings is especially prominent in specialized domains such as information technology, business, education, and media, where the pace of innovation and globalization demands constant linguistic updates. In the field of information technology, Uzbek has incorporated numerous English-derived terms such as kompyuter (computer), fayl (file), brauzer (browser), server, and onlayn

(online). These terms are not only adopted for practical use but are also adapted to Uzbek pronunciation and spelling norms. Many are used without translation due to the lack of exact Uzbek equivalents or because the English terms have become internationally recognized standards.

In business and economics, internationalisms like marketing, menedjment (management), brend (brand), startup, and investitsiya (investment) are widely used in both professional and academic contexts. These terms are often morphologically integrated into Uzbek grammar — for example, investitsiyalar (investments, plural form), or marketing strategiyasi (marketing strategy, with the possessive suffix -si).

The educational sector has also seen an influx of English borrowings, particularly with the spread of international programs and digital learning platforms. Words such as kurs (course), test, grant, sertifikat, and onlayn darslar (online lessons) have entered mainstream usage, often without full translation. These borrowings reflect changing practices in teaching, assessment, and credentialing, especially in universities and private education centers.

In media and pop culture, the impact is equally noticeable. English words like bloger (blogger), kontent (content), stream, like, and trend have become part of the everyday vocabulary of younger generations, especially those active on social media platforms.

Overall, these domains illustrate how English borrowings are not only filling lexical gaps but also reshaping how Uzbek speakers engage with modern concepts and global trends. The process of assimilation continues as new English terms enter the language and adapt to Uzbek linguistic norms over time.

In the result of language contacts the quantity of English borrowings, especially, international lexicon raising day by day. The growing influx of internationalisms of English origin is activating purists who are trying to free their native language from the dominance of foreign elements. In it's turn, national languages have to struggle for the purity of the language, and find equivalents in their the inner sources.

References

1. Давлятова Э.М. Лексические заимствования из западноевропейских языков в современном узбекском языке (на материале периодики) // Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. – 2011. №10 (225). Филология. Искусствоведения. Вып.52. С.34-37.

2. Данияров Р. Заимствование русско-интернациональных личных имен узбекским языком: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1967.
3. Добродомов И.Г. Заимствование // Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь / под общ.ред. В. Н. Ярцева. – М. : Сов.энциклопедия, 1990. – С. 158–159.
4. Крысин, Л. П. Русское слово, своё и чужое. – М.: Языки славянской культуры, 2004. – 883 с.
5. Кузнецова Э.В. Лексикология русского языка: Учеб. пособие для филол. фак. ун-тов. – М.: Высшая школа, 1989. – 216 с.
6. Лобковская Л.П. Интернационализмы как прецедентные имена // Казанская наука. Казань: Изд-во Казанский Издательский Дом, 2013. № 5. С. 114-117.
7. Мирзаев М. Советско-интернациональные слова в узбекской периодической прессе (1945-1950). Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук – Ташкент, 1951
8. ХУДАЙКУЛОВ, А. Э. (2019). Названия единиц измерения английского происхождения в текстах русских и узбекских письменных памятников: дюйм, фут. Иностранные языки в Узбекистане, (5), 112-122.
9. Худайкулов, А. Э. (2020). АНГЛИЦИЗМЫ С СУФФИКСОМ-ИНГ В ТЕКСТАХ УЗБЕКСКИХ ОФИЦИАЛЬНО-ДЕЛОВЫХ ДОКУМЕНТОВ. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (10-6), 75-78.
10. Филатова, М. И. (2015). АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК КАК ИСТОЧНИК ИНТЕРНАЦИОналиЗМОВ. ББК 74.584. 26 Т30, 371.
11. Davlyatova E.M. (2019). Borrowing as a Result of Cross-Cultural Interaction. GIS Business, 14(3), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.26643/gis.v14i3.1271>
12. David Roy Andrews «The how and why of some borrowings from English in third-wave émigré Russian». PhD dissert.– Michigan 1988, 153p.
13. einreich, Uriel. Languages in Contact: Findings and Problems. The Hague: Mouton and Co., 1964 – 149 pp.
14. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 27.02.2017 йилдаги 103-сон “Олий таълим муассасаларининг раҳбар ва педагог кадрларини қайта тайёрлаш ва уларнинг малакасини ошириш курслари тўғрисидаги Низомга ўзгартириш ва қўшимчалар киритиш ҳақида”ги қарори.

W